

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Legal and regulatory frameworks related to individual freedoms of speech and action

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable, first submitted in M12 as v1, provides a conceptual overview of some of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy from an institutional perspective. Module D focuses on the use of personal data and user profiling. Module E focuses on the control of individual speech and action. This version builds on v2 to begin to provide a toolkit to advance the state of the art in these two domains.

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3 Legal and Regulatory Frameworks

The purpose of this section of the deliverable is to provide an overview of how AI, big data and frontier technologies impact rights from the data protection perspective. The newly adopted definition of AI by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) states that “an AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that (can) influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment ” (OECD.AI, 2023).

On the one hand, big data is defined as “high-volume, high-velocity and high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making” (Definition of big data - Gartner Information Technology Glossary). On the other hand, the OECD defines frontier technologies as those which will “reshape industry and communications and provide urgently needed solutions to global challenges like climate change and have the potential to displace existing processes”. Frontier technologies include knowledge technologies such as blockchain, AI, IoT and VR (OECD Science, Technology and Industry Scoreboard, 2017). This section of the deliverable will focus on frontier technologies, as the current regulatory frameworks often do, however these frontier technologies include knowledge technologies.

The section will provide a legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies as well as the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising, and in particular, facial recognition as well as political advertising. It will also provide an analysis of the risks for data transfers to negatively impact democracy and fundamental rights and highlight the risks or challenges and opportunities in terms of rights and democracy with respect to frontier technologies with specific reference to their application in both the public and private sectors.

This deliverable aims to provide an overview of some of the problems which AI and big data pose to democracy from a perspective of government, organisations and companies. The use of frontier technologies by both private and public sector actors has increased and the use is being influenced by the application of big data (ICO, 2013a). The use of such technologies thus has an impact on privacy, data protection and other individual’s rights that are strengthened by different legal and regulatory frameworks (ICO, 2013b).

3.1 Applicable Legal and Regulatory Framework

This subsection concerns the legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable as well as proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies in addition to the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising, particularly facial recognition and political advertising.

The legal framework that will be discussed includes the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the ePrivacy Directive, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (the Charter), the AI Act, the Digital Services Act package, and 2021/0381 (COD) Transparency and targeting of political advertising.

There are also significant sector-specific regulations on AI for which we have prepared a review that has mapped the various instruments. While the following sections provide information on applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies, a broader set of guidelines on relevant legal and ethical frameworks applicable to AI are provided in Appendix I. For the purpose of this T4.1, we have selected the following guidelines which we will discuss due to their relevance: EU AI Strategy, the High-level Expert Group (HLEG) Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy and Ethical AI, the EU Commission's White Paper on AI and the AI Act .

Each piece of legislation will be analysed to the extent they regulate applications of AI & big data (and specifically, profiling, targeted and political advertising, and facial recognition) with the aim of upholding fundamental rights and democracy.

3.1.1 EU Legal Data Protection Framework: The General Data Protection Regulation and the ePrivacy Directive

The GDPR is the world's most comprehensive and progressive data protection law. Privacy and data protection as rights are enshrined in the EU Treaties and in the Charter. Article 8 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (ECHR) protects the right to respect for private life, the home and correspondence. This includes protecting the privacy of messages, phone calls, and emails.

The scope of application of the GDPR is in relation to data processing activities that take place using the information which relates to an identified or identifiable individual called a data subject located within the EU. Article 4(1) of the GDPR defines an identifiable individual as one who can be identified either directly or indirectly by reference to an identifier e.g., name, location data, an online identifier etc.

The GDPR covers two types of personal data, i.e., common personal data such as name, surname, location data, financial information, etc. and also, special categories of personal data under Article 9 of the GDPR. Special categories of data require a higher level of protection. They include genetic data, health data, biometric data, information about race or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership and information on sex life or sexual orientation.

The ePrivacy Directive is a legal instrument that sets the standard for all entities which store or access information stored in the terminal equipment of a subscriber or user in the EEA. A terminal equipment under the ePrivacy Directive is defined as that which is directly or indirectly connected to the interface of a public telecommunications network to send, process or receive information, or a satellite earth equipment.

In general, the ePrivacy Directive and the GDPR help ensure digital privacy for residents of the EU. The ePrivacy Directive requires EU countries to ensure that users grant their consent before cookies are stored and accessed in computers, smartphones or another device connected to the Internet. A cookie is a small file, typically of letters and numbers, downloaded onto a device when the user accesses certain websites (ICO, 2012).

The GDPR and ePrivacy Directive regulate profiling and targeted advertising (in particular, facial recognition, political advertising) by providing for certain conditions to be met, such as ensuring users' informed consent. Consent of data subjects is the legal basis for advertising. Article 4(11) of the GDPR requires consent to be a freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of data subjects' wishes, given through a statement or a clear affirmative action. Similarly, the ePrivacy Directive requires users' consent for cookies and other tracking devices that interfere with the users' terminal equipment.

3.1.1.1 The General Data Protection Regulation

Article 85 of the GDPR recognizes the need for the protection of freedom of expression and grants EU Member States the power to adopt, where necessary, statutory derogations to a large part of the GDPR itself, including data processing principles, data subject's rights and rules on international transfers. In the EU, privacy and data protection are commonly recognised as important components for a sustainable democracy (Data Protection, EDPS).

Although privacy is among the rights enshrined in the ECHR, the GDPR has shaped the protection of democracy due to the fact that entities have an obligation to demonstrate what personal data they are processing. In order to retain trust and confidence of the public and the integrity of the elections, organisations involved in political campaigning and political aspirants must use personal data and campaigning techniques in ways that are transparent and informed (Democracy disrupted? Personal information and political influence-ICO, 2018). The transparency principle and the right to information of the data subjects are requirements for processing of personal data under the GDPR (see Arts. 5(1)(a), 12, 13, and 14 GDPR).

Political opinions are among the special categories of personal data that are accorded protection under Article 9 of the GDPR. As a general rule, processing such data listed above is prohibited. However, under certain limitations, an entity may be allowed to process sensitive personal data. They include:

- Where sensitive data has been manifestly made public;
- Where the data subject has given their explicit consent;
- Where there is a law which governs a specific type of data processing for a specific purpose related to public interest or health;
- Where a law including adequate safeguards provides for the processing of sensitive personal data in areas such as public health, employment and social protection.

In general, effective data protection and meaningful privacy rights support democratic processes, participation and debate (Joint Statement on Privacy and Democratic Rights- OPCC, 2023).

3.1.1.1.1 The Importance of Data Protection in AI

In recent years, AI has gone through rapid development and has provided opportunities for economic, social, and cultural development. The opportunities are accompanied by serious risks e.g.,

unemployment, inequality, discrimination, social exclusion, surveillance, and manipulation (The impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on artificial intelligence - EPRS, 2020a). This necessitates the need for effective regulation of AI. Furthermore, several AI systems process personal data. The personal data may be used as data sets to train the machine learning systems i.e., to build algorithmic models. Personal data may also be to infer certain habits concerning individuals.

The GDPR does not explicitly mention AI. However several GDPR provisions are directly applicable to the deployment of AI systems. The GDPR principles and rights can be interpreted in a manner that is compatible with AI and big data. For example, the right to information of data subjects under Article 13 GDPR should enable data subjects to understand the purpose of each AI-based processing and its limits (EPRS, 2020b).

Similarly, the principles of data protection by design and by default under Article 25 GDPR should be taken into consideration in the development of AI and will not hinder their development in the case where the AI systems are correctly designed and implemented (EPRS, 2020c).

The obligation to carry out a DPIA under Article 35 GDPR where the processing of personal data is likely to result in a high risk is likely required when looking into the deployment of AI systems to process personal data.¹

The State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information in Baden-Württemberg in its Discussion paper on when and how personal data may be processed for the training and application of AI noted that the processing of large sets of personal data in AI systems bears the risk that the data will become special categories of personal data over the course of the processing lifecycle (LfDI BW, 2023). The requirements for processing of special categories of personal data under Article 9 GDPR should thus be taken into consideration. Generally, the citizens' trust in the ability to innovate and use AI systems in a responsible manner requires that data protection requirements are implemented.

3.1.1.1.1 Data Protection Principles and Other Relevant Aspects of Data Protection Law

The GDPR outlines key principles which influence other rules and obligations set out in the legislation. Compliance with the fundamental principles of data protection is a step towards ensuring the fulfilment of obligations under the GDPR. The data protection principles set out in Article 5 of the GDPR help redress the imbalance between the individuals and the entities that process personal data.

¹ As stated in D8.3, note that "Article 35 GDPR requires that DPIAs are carried out in certain cases; specifically where a data processing activity and specifically a new technology, is 'likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons'. DPIAs therefore do not need to be carried out for all data processing activities. That being said, DPIAs represent a useful accountability tool which can be relied upon by data controllers to ensure data protection compliance." Activities which may be considered to be highly risky include profiling, the "processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10", the "Innovative use or applying technological or organisational solutions" and "data processed on a large scale". See Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, 4 April 2017.

Compliance with the data protection principles and data protection law in general, preserves democracy while also protecting the individual in the face of development of frontier technologies and generates trust in the digital economy (Data Protection Principles-Jersey Office of the Information Commissioner, 2019). The data protection principles will be explained in relation to enhancing democracy in the subsequent sections. However a more detailed description of the data processing principles is set out in the Data Management Plan, D1.1.

3.1.1.1.1.2 Lawfulness, Fairness and Transparency

Article 5(1)(a) of the GDPR requires that personal data is processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject. The processing of personal data for various operations must include a legal basis pursuant to Article 6 of the GDPR. At least one valid lawful basis must exist for the lawful processing of personal data which must be determined prior to the processing of personal data. Legal bases under Article 6 GDPR include consent, contractual necessity, for compliance with a legal obligation, to protect the vital interests of a data subject or other person, for the performance of a task in the public interests, and for the purpose of legitimate interest.

Transparency in processing operations entails being clear, open and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller, what they intend to do with the personal data and why they need to process the specific personal data. All this should be made clear prior to the processing operations (ICO, n.p.)

Fairness implies that the processing of personal data shall be done in a way in which the data subjects may reasonably expect their data to be processed and may not be used in an unlawful manner. Fairness also entails that data is not used in a manner that would have unjustified effects on data subjects (ICO, n.p.).

In enhancing democracy, fairness relates to developing a regulatory framework where the rights of the citizens with respect to their personal data are respected and the existing inequality in bargaining power between them and governments and companies that process their personal data are mitigated. In such a framework, the individual must have control over their personal data since they are the data principal in the digital economy (Committee of Experts under the Chairmanship of Justice B.N. Srikrishna, 2018: 14a). The relationship between the individual and entities with whom the individual shares their personal data is based on a fundamental expectation of trust (Committee of Experts under the Chairmanship of Justice B.N. Srikrishna, 2018: 14b). The individual thus expects that their personal data will be used fairly, in a manner that fulfils their interest and is reasonably foreseeable.

Some of the principles for reforms to enhance accountability of frontier technologies, including providing robust protection for citizens' privacy include increasing transparency about platform's algorithms (The White House, 2023). These principles are important in ensuring that individuals are involved in decision making concerning their personal data and to ensure that states and entities that gather and record citizens personal data are transparent about the data they have followed fair and lawful processes in the collection, use, retention and maintenance of security of that data (Article 19, 2017).

3.1.1.1.3 Purpose Limitation, Data Minimisation, Storage Limitation

The purpose limitation principle under Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR requires personal data to be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with the original purposes. Instead, the principle of data minimisation established under Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR requires the data controller to limit personal data to what is directly relevant and necessary in order to achieve a specific purpose for which the data are processed (ICO, n.p.).

The storage limitation principle under Article 5(1)(e) GDPR requires that personal data is only kept in a form that allows for the identification of data subjects for as long as is necessary for the purposes of processing of personal data. These principles specifically aim to reduce risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals (ICO, n.p.).

3.1.1.1.4 Necessity and Proportionality

Necessity is an important principle in assessing the restriction of fundamental rights e.g., the right to the protection of personal data. It is also important when assessing the lawfulness of the processing of personal data. The processing of personal data shall only be carried out when necessary and the duration in which the data is stored shall be necessary for the purpose of processing (EDPS, 2020a).

The principle of proportionality is a general principle enshrined in EU law which restricts governments, companies and organisations in the exercise of their powers by requiring them to strike a balance between the means used and the aim they intend to achieve (EDPS, 2020b).

Proportionality is fundamental for the limitation of fundamental rights such as the right to the protection of personal data (EDPS, 2020c). Proportionality requires that only personal data that is adequate and relevant for the purposes of processing is collected and processed.

3.1.1.1.5 Accuracy

Article 5(1)(d) of the GDPR outlines the principle of accuracy which requires that personal data is accurate and kept up to date. This places an obligation on entities to rectify or erase inaccurate data without delay. Where the accuracy of personal data is contested by the data subject, Article 18(1) of the GDPR gives a data subject the right to obtain a restriction of processing of their personal data. In order to enhance access to information for citizens, governments must establish an accurate record keeping system.

3.1.1.1.1.6 Integrity and Confidentiality – Data Security

Article 5(1)(f) of the GDPR necessitates that personal data is processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of personal data. The principle also requires protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage. The data security principle has been reaffirmed in Article 32 GDPR. This article necessitates that appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure a level of security which is appropriate to the risk which arises as a result of the data processing activity. Data security measures and online restrictions that are implemented by governments, organisations or companies must align with international human rights law and standards and this includes the protection against among other things, unethical hacking, data interception and identity theft (Open Internet for Democracy, 2023).

3.1.1.1.1.7 Accountability

The accountability principle under Article 5(2) of the GDPR places a requirement on data controllers to be able to demonstrate compliance with other data protection principles. The Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679 re-affirm that data controllers must also comply with the accountability principle under the GDPR which should be applied throughout the life cycle of data processing.

The principle of accountability is an important piece of good governance that enables the citizens to gain control over the use of public resources. It contributes to limiting the risk of abuse of power and corrupt practices, which in turn guarantees the fulfilment of citizens' rights. Where governments, organisations and companies have a well-functioning accountability mechanism, it enhances trust in the management of citizens affairs. The accountability principle thus places an obligation on the relevant actors including governments, to inform the public and justify their decisions. This places an information obligation on the actors and is related to the rights of the citizens to get information and get an explanation relating to the actions of governments, organisations and companies.

3.1.1.1.1.8 Data Protection by Design and by Default

Article 25 of the GDPR lays down the principle of data protection by design. The principle requires the data controller, at the time of determination of the means for processing and during the processing itself, to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures which are designed to implement data protection principles in an effective manner in order to meet the requirements of the GDPR. The principle also requires the controller to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure that, by default, only personal data which is necessary for a specific purpose is processed.

When governments, organisations and companies enable the principle of data protection by design and by default in the building of systems, they will build foundations of trustworthy data sharing (Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon, et al., 2020a). Governments, organisations and companies should build a workflow based on trust as a fundamental consideration in order to facilitate data sharing and ultimately, create benefit to individuals and society at large (Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon, et al., 2020b).

3.1.1.1.2 Data Protection Rights

Chapter III of the GDPR recognizes the rights of data subjects, including the right to be informed, the right of access to their personal data, the right to rectification of inaccurate information about them, the right to erasure or the right to be forgotten, the right to restriction of processing, the right to data portability, the right to object to the processing of their personal data, and the right of data subjects to not be subjected to decisions based solely on automated processing including profiling which produces legal or similar effects (see Articles 12, 15-22 GDPR).

These data protection rights are not absolute rights and certain data protection rights only apply in certain circumstances. For example, the right to erasure only applies where personal data is no longer required for the purpose it was originally collected. Recital 4 of the GDPR provides that the right to protection of personal data must be considered in relation to its function in society and balanced against other fundamental rights.

The GDPR facilitates access to justice in multiple ways and facilitates the fight against discrimination (ICT Insider, 2024). This has been demonstrated through the provisions that allow for the exercise of data subjects' rights and have ultimately led to enforcement actions by the EU Supervisory Authorities. An example of such an enforcement action is the fine of EUR 1.9 million issued by the Bremen Data Protection Authority against a Bremen-based housing company which was found to have unlawfully processed the personal data of over 9,500 potential tenants (BREBAU GmbH, 2022). The company processed data such as skin colour, information relating to the health of the data subjects and sexual orientation and failed to respond to the requests from data subjects. This resulted in the issuance of a fine against the company.

Essentially, the exercise of the rights of data subjects facilitate the access to justice of individuals and promote healthy democratic practices such as promoting an environment that protects individuals from discrimination based on certain factors such as their political affiliations.

3.1.1.1.3 Risks and Opportunities

There are a number of risks and opportunities for individuals that may be presented and need to be carefully considered in the application of the data protection legislation. More specifically, the discussion on vulnerable groups of persons arises due to the inequality, power imbalances and social injustices (Gianclaudio, et al., 2020a). Vulnerable groups are persons who are often considered to be legally incompetent, persons who cannot give their consent, or persons that may suffer adverse consequences in the case where their data became publicly available (Ethics in Social Science and Humanities Guidelines, 2021). The Article 29 Working Party (WP29), now known as the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) affirms that the key factor in identifying individual vulnerability is the existence of a power imbalance between the data subject and the data controller (Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk, Article 29 Working Party). The WP29 lists some of the vulnerable data subjects to include children due to the fact that they are not able to knowingly consent or object to the processing of their personal data. Employees, mentally ill persons, asylum seekers, the elderly and patients are also considered to be vulnerable groups and require special protection.

In the data protection framework, vulnerable groups emerge from the possible harms to which individuals are exposed to. Data driven systems may be tools of potential discrimination which may ultimately lead to physical and psychological harms (Gianclaudio, et al., 2020b). There are several examples from law enforcement, banking, welfare, recruitment and housing that have demonstrated that technologies can contribute to social inequalities and lead to discrimination in the access to goods and services. An example of an enforcement action from the Dutch Data Protection Authority that demonstrates the effects of discrimination posed by the deployment of technologies include the EUR 2.75 million on the Dutch tax authorities (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021a). According to the DPA, for several years the Tax and Customs Administration has processed the (dual) nationality of applicants for childcare allowance in an unlawful, discriminatory, and therefore improper manner, resulting in serious violations of the GDPR (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021b).

In January 2014, such data should have already been deleted but in May 2018, it was found that the dual nationality of 1,4 million people was still registered in the system of the tax authorities (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021c). The Dutch tax authorities had processed this personal data (i.e., dual nationality) for three main reasons i.e., to assess whether an application for child benefits should be granted (such data on nationality was stored in the Benefits system (TVS), to combat organised fraud; and to determine whether certain tax-benefit applications were of a high-risk (i.e., not granting tax benefit because nationality is linked to an extremist group) (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021d). Ultimately, if data protection rights in the use of frontier technologies are not carefully considered and implemented, it may adversely impact data subjects.

Specific attention needs to be given in the processing of personal data belonging to vulnerable groups with regards to the obligations of data controllers. For example, WP29 Opinion on legitimate interests notes that when data controllers are performing the balance test that is required in order to process personal data on the basis of legitimate interests (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR), they need to consider the status of the data controller and data subject, including the “balance of power between the data subject and the data controller, or whether the data subject is a child or otherwise belongs to a more vulnerable segment of the population” (Article 29 WP, 2014).

Ultimately, in the case cited above, the tax authorities acted in a discriminatory way. In each of the three scenarios, under which dual nationality of citizens was processed, it was found that such data is irrelevant. The Dutch DPA emphasised the fact that the improper processing of one’s nationality not only infringed the GDPR but also infringed the fundamental right to not be discriminated against (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021e).

Data controllers must therefore specifically pay attention to their special obligations towards vulnerable groups in order to avoid data processing related risks. For instance, the principle of transparency which requires information addressed to the data subject to be concise, easily accessible and easy to understand, and plain language used should be taken into account in the processing of personal data belonging to vulnerable groups.

3.1.2 EU AI Strategy

The EU AI strategy's objective is to make the EU a world class hub for AI and also ensure that AI is human-centric and trustworthy (Shaping Europe's digital future, European Commission). The aim translates into the European approach to excellence and trust through concrete rules and actions. Building trustworthy AI systems will create an innovation-friendly environment for users, developers and deployers and the EC proposed three key pillars that will enhance building trustworthy AI (European Commission, 2024a).

- A legal framework for AI that will uphold fundamental rights and address safety risks specific to the AI systems (European Commission, 2023). On 12 July 2024, the Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) was published in the EU Official Journal. This Act aims to provide AI developers, deployers and users with clear requirements and obligations relating to the use of AI (Official Journal of the European Union, 2024). ;
- A civil liability framework — adapting liability rules to the digital age and AI. This will ensure among other things that victims are compensated for damages caused by unsafe products, including digital products and AI systems (European Commission, n.p.); and
- The revision of sectoral safety legislation (European Commission, 2024b).

3.1.2.1 Trustworthy and Ethical AI

As part of its initial work on AI, the European Commission established the High-level Expert Group on AI (HLEG). The Group produced a total of four deliverables:

- Deliverable 1: Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (HLEG, 2019a)– these Guidelines suggest taking a “human-centric approach on AI” and establish a set of seven requirements for trustworthy AI;
- Deliverable 2: Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI (HLEG, 2019b) – this document contains 33 “recommendations to guide trustworthy AI towards sustainability, growth, competitiveness, and inclusion” ad aim to “empower, benefit and protect European citizens”;
- Deliverable 3: The final Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) – the ALTAI² is an innovative online tool which permits developers to carry out a self-assessment against the Ethics Guidelines;

² See <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

- Deliverable 4: Sectoral Considerations on the Policy and Investment Recommendations – this document provides information on ways to implement the recommendations provided in the above documents.

This subsection will provide a brief introduction into the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

3.1.2.1.1 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI

The HLEG’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, published on 8 April 2019 recall that trustworthy AI must first be lawful, in that it must comply with all legal requirements (HLEG, 2019: 2a). Second, AI must be ethical, meaning that it must adhere to values and ethical principles and third, it must be robust both socially and technically to account for unintentional harms which may be realized (HLEG, 2019: 2b). From the technical perspective, being robust entails that “the system’s technical robustness as appropriate in a given context, such as the application domain or life cycle phase”, and from a social perspective, it entails taking into consideration the environment and context of the AI system (HLEG, 2019: 7).

Throughout the design, development, and deployment of AI, these factors must be considered. Specifically, adherence to ethical principles include ensuring that the AI system is fair, that human autonomy is respected, that harm is prevented, and that systems can be explained (HLEG, 2019: 2c). Furthermore, disadvantaged or vulnerable groups should be specifically considered (HLEG, 2019: 2d). This is particularly important in situations where a power asymmetry may be present such as in the employment context (HLEG, 2019: 2e). To this end, specific risk management processes and procedures should be put in place to mitigate potential risks arising from the use of AI (HLEG, 2019: 2e).

The seven requirements for trustworthy AI outlined by the HLEG are:

1. human agency and oversight,
2. technical robustness and safety,
3. privacy and data governance,
4. transparency,
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness,
6. environmental and societal well-being, and
7. accountability (Ibid).

These requirements must be taken into consideration throughout the lifecycle of AI, i.e., from design and development through the deployment phases (HLEG, 2019: 2f). In order to ensure this, clear policies and procedures must be established and followed.

The limitations and capabilities of AI systems must be clear and individuals should always be informed that they are interacting with an AI system (HLEG, 2019: 3a). Furthermore, AI systems must be auditable and decisions made by it traceable, a requirement which takes on particular relevance in situations where rights may be impacted (HLEG, 2019: 3b). It is considered a best practice to involve different stakeholders in the development of systems, which may contribute to identifying potential harms.

Importantly, due to the fact that “there might be fundamental tensions between different principles and requirements”, it is necessary to “Continuously identify, evaluate, document and communicate these trade-offs and their solutions” (HLEG, 2019: 3c).

Assessment lists such as the ALTAI (HLEG, 2020c) may be relied upon, bearing in mind that no assessment is entirely complete and should be part of a continuous monitoring process, if possible also involving affected stakeholders and experts with diverse types of knowledge to ensure comprehensiveness to the extent possible.

The ALTAI (HLEG, 2020b) is meant to be completed with the assistance of designers and developers of the AI system, management, legal and/or compliance officers, data scientists, procurement specialists, and front-end staff who will use/work with the system.

As a first step, it is suggested that a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) is carried out (HLEG, 2020: 5). The FRIA is meant to examine the impact of the AI system on fundamental rights such as those provided in the European Convention on Human Rights. The HLEG suggests the following questions as a basis for the FRIA:

“1. Does the AI system potentially negatively discriminate against people on the basis of any of the following grounds (non-exhaustively): sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential negative discrimination (bias) during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential negative discrimination (bias) in the AI system?

2. Does the AI system respect the rights of the child, for example with respect to child protection and taking the child’s best interests into account?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential harm to children by the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential harm to children during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

3. Does the AI system protect personal data relating to individuals in line with GDPR? Have you put in place processes to assess in detail the need for a data protection impact assessment, including an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing

operations in relation to their purpose, with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

4. Does the AI system respect the freedom of expression and information and/or freedom of assembly and association?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, in the AI system?" (HLEG, 2020: 5-6).

Article 27 of the AI Act (discussed in more detail below) also includes the requirement to carry out a FRIA for high-risk AI systems deployed in public bodies and services. The AI Office shall develop a template for a questionnaire, including through an automated tool, to facilitate deployers in carrying out a FRIA in a simplified manner. This is a positive development aimed at upholding fundamental rights also when AI is used.

Following the completion of the FRIA, the ALTAI contains sample questions concerning Human Agency and Autonomy, Human Oversight, Resilience to Attack and Security, General Safety, Accuracy, Reliability, Fall-back plans and Reproducibility, Privacy and Data Governance, Transparency, Traceability, Explainability, Communication, Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness, Avoidance of Unfair Bias, Accessibility and Universal Design, Stakeholder Participation, Societal and Environmental Well-being, Impact on Work and Skills, Impact on Society at large or Democracy, Accountability, Auditability, and Risk Management. All AI systems must be subjected to such assessments.

In relation to democracy specifically, the section of the template assessment serves to address the impact of AI on society and democracy which the HLEG states serves particular attention in relation "to the democratic processes, including not only political decision-making but also electoral contexts (e.g. when AI systems amplify fake news, segregate the electorate, facilitate totalitarian behaviour, etc.)" (HLEG, 2020, p. 20). The Group suggests evaluating, e.g.:

- If the AI system could have a negative impact on society in general or on democracy;
- If the societal impact beyond end-users has been considered;
- If actions have been taken to minimise potential societal harms;
- If measures have been taken to ensure that the AI does not have any negative impacts on democracy (Ibid).

The HLEG also provides a general template checklist (see Table 1) which can be used by organisations, organised in the table below. This accountability exercise should be carried out by deployers and developers of AI systems on a regular basis as suggested above.

Table 1 – HLEG Trustworthy AI Assessment List (Pilot Version)

Table Source: pp. 26-31 HLEG 2019a³

1. Human Agency and Oversight
a. Fundamental rights
Did you carry out a fundamental rights impact assessment where there could be a negative impact on fundamental rights?
Did you identify and document potential trade-offs made between the different principles and rights?
Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the (end) user’s decision-making process in an unintended way?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Did you consider whether the AI system should communicate to (end) users that a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision? · In case of a chatbot or other conversational system, are the human end users made aware that they are interacting with a non-human agent?
b. Human agency
Is the AI system implemented in work and labour process? If so, did you consider the task allocation between the AI system and humans for meaningful interactions and appropriate human oversight and control?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Does the AI system enhance or augment human capabilities? · Did you take safeguards to prevent overconfidence in or overreliance on the AI system for work processes?
c. Human oversight
Did you consider the appropriate level of human control for the particular AI system and use case?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Can you describe the level of human control or involvement? · Who is the “human in control” and what are the moments or tools for human intervention? · Did you put in place mechanisms and measures to ensure human control or oversight?

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

- Did you take any measures to enable audit and to remedy issues related to governing AI autonomy?

Is there is a self-learning or autonomous AI system or use case? If so, did you put in place more specific mechanisms of control and oversight?

- Which detection and response mechanisms did you establish to assess whether something could go wrong?
- Did you ensure a stop button or procedure to safely abort an operation where needed? Does this procedure abort the process entirely, in part, or delegate control to a human?

2. Technical robustness and safety

a. Resilience to attack and security

Did you assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable?

- Did you consider different types and natures of vulnerabilities, such as data pollution, physical infrastructure, cyber-attacks?

Did you put measures or systems in place to ensure the integrity and resilience of the AI system against potential attacks?

Did you verify how your system behaves in unexpected situations and environments?

Did you consider to what degree your system could be dual-use? If so, did you take suitable preventative measures against this case (including for instance not publishing the research or deploying the system)?

b. Fallback plan and general safety

Did you ensure that your system has a sufficient fallback plan if it encounters adversarial attacks or other unexpected situations (for example technical switching procedures or asking for a human operator before proceeding)?

Did you consider the level of risk raised by the AI system in this specific use case?

- Did you put any process in place to measure and assess risks and safety?
- Did you provide the necessary information in case of a risk for human physical integrity?
- Did you consider an insurance policy to deal with potential damage from the AI system?
- Did you identify potential safety risks of (other) foreseeable uses of the technology, including accidental or malicious misuse? Is there a plan to mitigate or manage these risks?

Did you assess whether there is a probable chance that the AI system may cause damage or harm to users or third parties? Did you assess the likelihood, potential damage, impacted audience and severity?

- **Did you consider the liability and consumer protection rules, and take them into account?**
- **Did you consider the potential impact or safety risk to the environment or to animals?**
- **Did your risk analysis include whether security or network problems such as cybersecurity hazards could pose safety risks or damage due to unintentional behaviour of the AI system?**

Did you estimate the likely impact of a failure of your AI system when it provides wrong results, becomes unavailable, or provides societally unacceptable results (for example discrimination)?

- **Did you define thresholds and did you put governance procedures in place to trigger alternative/fallback plans?**
- **Did you define and test fallback plans?**

c. Accuracy

Did you assess what level and definition of accuracy would be required in the context of the AI system and use case?

- **Did you assess how accuracy is measured and assured?**
- **Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data used is comprehensive and up to date?**
- **Did you put in place measures in place to assess whether there is a need for additional data, for example to improve accuracy or to eliminate bias?**

Did you verify what harm would be caused if the AI system makes inaccurate predictions?

Did you put in place ways to measure whether your system is making an unacceptable amount of inaccurate predictions?

Did you put in place a series of steps to increase the system's accuracy?

d. Reliability and reproducibility

Did you put in place a strategy to monitor and test if the AI system is meeting the goals, purposes and intended applications?

- **Did you test whether specific contexts or particular conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility?**
- **Did you put in place verification methods to measure and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility?**
- **Did you put in place processes to describe when an AI system fails in certain types of settings?**

- Did you clearly document and operationalise these processes for the testing and verification of the reliability of AI systems?
- Did you establish mechanisms of communication to assure (end-)users of the system's reliability?

3. Privacy and data governance

a. Respect for privacy and data Protection

Depending on the use case, did you establish a mechanism allowing others to flag issues related to privacy or data protection in the AI system's processes of data collection (for training and operation) and data processing?

Did you assess the type and scope of data in your data sets (for example whether they contain personal data)?

Did you consider ways to develop the AI system or train the model without or with minimal use of potentially sensitive or personal data?

Did you build in mechanisms for notice and control over personal data depending on the use case (such as valid consent and possibility to revoke, when applicable)?

Did you take measures to enhance privacy, such as via encryption, anonymisation and aggregation?

Where a Data Privacy Officer (DPO) exists, did you involve this person at an early stage in the process?

b. Quality and integrity of data

Did you align your system with relevant standards (for example ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for daily data management and governance?

Did you establish oversight mechanisms for data collection, storage, processing and use?

Did you assess the extent to which you are in control of the quality of the external data sources used?

Did you put in place processes to ensure the quality and integrity of your data? Did you consider other processes? How are you verifying that your data sets have not been compromised or hacked?

c. Access to data

What protocols, processes and procedures did you follow to manage and ensure proper data governance?

- **Did you assess who can access users' data, and under what circumstances?**
- **Did you ensure that these persons are qualified and required to access the data, and that they have the necessary competences to understand the details of data protection policy?**
- **Did you ensure an oversight mechanism to log when, where, how, by whom and for what purpose data was accessed?**

4. Transparency

a. Traceability

- **Did you establish measures that can ensure traceability?**
 - o **This could entail documenting the following methods: Methods used for designing and developing the algorithmic system:**
 - § **Rule-based AI systems: the method of programming or how the model was built;**
 - § **Learning-based AI systems; the method of training the algorithm, including which input data was gathered and selected, and how this occurred.**
 - o **Methods used to test and validate the algorithmic system:**
 - § **Rule-based AI systems; the scenarios or cases used in order to test and validate;**
 - § **Learning-based model: information about the data used to test and validate.**
 - o **Outcomes of the algorithmic system:**
 - § **The outcomes of or decisions taken by the algorithm, as well as potential other decisions that would result from different cases (for example, for other subgroups of users).**

b. Explainability

Did you assess:

- **to what extent the decisions and hence the outcome made by the AI system can be understood?**
- **to what degree the system's decision influences the organisation's decision-making processes?**
- **why this particular system was deployed in this specific area?**
- **what the system's business model is (for example, how does it create value for the organisation)?**

Did you ensure an explanation as to why the system took a certain choice resulting in a certain outcome that all users can understand?

Did you design the AI system with interpretability in mind from the start?

- **Did you research and try to use the simplest and most interpretable model possible for the application in question?**
- **Did you assess whether you can analyse your training and testing data? Can you change and update this over time?**
- **Did you assess whether you can examine interpretability after the model's training and development, or whether you have access to the internal workflow of the model?**

c. Communication

Did you communicate to (end-)users – through a disclaimer or any other means – that they are interacting with an AI system and not with another human? Did you label your AI system as such?

Did you establish mechanisms to inform (end-)users on the reasons and criteria behind the AI system's outcomes?

- **Did you communicate this clearly and intelligibly to the intended audience?**
- **Did you establish processes that consider users' feedback and use this to adapt the system?**
- **Did you communicate around potential or perceived risks, such as bias?**
- **Depending on the use case, did you consider communication and transparency towards other audiences, third parties or the general public?**

Did you clarify the purpose of the AI system and who or what may benefit from the product/service?

- **Did you specify usage scenarios for the product and clearly communicate these to ensure that it is understandable and appropriate for the intended audience?**
- **Depending on the use case, did you think about human psychology and potential limitations, such as risk of confusion, confirmation bias or cognitive fatigue?**

Did you clearly communicate characteristics, limitations and potential shortcomings of the AI system?

- **In case of the system's development: to whoever is deploying it into a product or service?**
- **In case of the system's deployment: to the (end-)user or consumer?**

5. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

a. Unfair bias avoidance

Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?

- **Did you assess and acknowledge the possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets?**
- **Did you consider diversity and representativeness of users in the data? Did you test for specific populations or problematic use cases?**
- **Did you research and use available technical tools to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?**
- **Did you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the development, deployment and use phase of the system?**

Depending on the use case, did you ensure a mechanism that allows others to flag issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

- **Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?**
- **Did you consider others, potentially indirectly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end)- users?**

Did you assess whether there is any possible decision variability that can occur under the same conditions?

- **If so, did you consider what the possible causes of this could be?**
- **In case of variability, did you establish a measurement or assessment mechanism of the potential impact of such variability on fundamental rights?**

Did you ensure an adequate working definition of “fairness” that you apply in designing AI systems?

- **Is your definition commonly used? Did you consider other definitions before choosing this one?**
- **Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?**
- **Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI systems? Did you consider other potential mechanisms?**

b. Accessibility and universal design

Did you ensure that the AI system accommodates a wide range of individual preferences and abilities?

- **Did you assess whether the AI system is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? How was this designed into the system and how is it verified?**
- **Did you ensure that information about the AI system is accessible also to users of assistive technologies?**

- **Did you involve or consult this community during the development phase of the AI system?**

Did you take the impact of your AI system on the potential user audience into account?

- **Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system is representative of your target user audience? Is it representative of the wider population, considering also of other groups who might tangentially be impacted?**
- **Did you assess whether there could be persons or groups who might be disproportionately affected by negative implications?**
- **Did you get feedback from other teams or groups that represent different backgrounds and experiences?**

c. Stakeholder participation

Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of different stakeholders in the AI system's development and use?

Did you pave the way for the introduction of the AI system in your organisation by informing and involving impacted workers and their representatives in advance?

6. Societal and environmental well-being

a. Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI

Did you establish mechanisms to measure the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and use (for example the type of energy used by the data centres)?

Did you ensure measures to reduce the environmental impact of your AI system's life cycle?

b. Social impact

In case the AI system interacts directly with humans:

- **Did you assess whether the AI system encourages humans to develop attachment and empathy towards the system?**
- **Did you ensure that the AI system clearly signals that its social interaction is simulated and that it has no capacities of "understanding" and "feeling"?**

Did you ensure that the social impacts of the AI system are well understood? For example, did you assess whether there is a risk of job loss or de-skilling of the workforce? What steps have been taken to counteract such risks?

c. Society and democracy

Did you assess the broader societal impact of the AI system's use beyond the individual (end-)user, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders?

7. Accountability

a. Auditability

Did you establish mechanisms that facilitate the system's auditability, such as ensuring traceability and logging of the AI system's processes and outcomes?

Did you ensure, in applications affecting fundamental rights (including safety-critical applications) that the AI system can be audited independently?

b. Minimising and reporting negative Impact

Did you carry out a risk or impact assessment of the AI system, which takes into account different stakeholders that are (in)directly affected?

Did you provide training and education to help develop accountability practices?

- Which workers or branches of the team are involved? Does it go beyond the development phase?
- Do these trainings also teach the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?
- Did you consider establishing an 'ethical AI review board' or a similar mechanism to discuss overall accountability and ethics practices, including potentially unclear grey areas?

Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or put in place auditing processes to oversee ethics and accountability, in addition to internal initiatives?

Did you establish processes for third parties (e.g. suppliers, consumers, distributors/vendors) or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system?

c. Documenting trade-offs

Did you establish a mechanism to identify relevant interests and values implicated by the AI system and potential trade-offs between them?

How do you decide on such trade-offs? Did you ensure that the trade-off decision was documented?

d. Ability to redress

Did you establish an adequate set of mechanisms that allows for redress in case of the occurrence of any harm or adverse impact?

Did you put mechanisms in place both to provide information to (end-)users/third parties about opportunities for redress?

3.1.2.2 Commission's White Paper on AI

In 2020, the European Commission (EC) released “A White paper on Artificial Intelligence — A European approach to excellence and trust” which aims at providing a definition of AI, outlines its benefits and technological advances in different areas e.g., medicine, security and farming, as well as identifying potential risks. Some of the potential risks laid out include gender inequality, discrimination and lack of privacy (European Commission, 2020a).

The White Paper recognizes that AI is grounded in values and fundamental rights such as human dignity and privacy protection and thus technologies have to be developed in compliance with the rules in order to protect citizens rights and to give them confidence in the use of their data by government, organisations and companies. The EC emphasised the importance of enhancing digital literacy for all citizens and raising awareness relating to data privacy, transparency, the definition of AI, data governance, responsibility, and trust and dual-use of technologies (European Commission, 2020b). This will have an overall positive effect in fostering democracy for the citizens.

3.1.2.3 EU AI Act

On 12 July 2024, the AI Act was published in the EU Official Journal and entered into force 20 days after its publication on 1 August 2024. It establishes harmonised rules for the market placement, service initiation, and use of AI systems across the EU. The Act covers a range of areas, including prohibitions on certain AI practices, specific requirements for high-risk AI systems and obligations regarding transparency.

The regulation aims at ensuring that fundamental rights, democracy, the rule of law and environmental sustainability are shielded from high-risk AI, while at the same time boosting innovation and making the EU a leader in the field (European Parliament, 2023a). It aims to foster the development of safe and trustworthy AI systems across the EU's single market by both private and public actors and provides guidelines and obligations for both AI developers and deployers (the latter concerning the entities that use an AI system for their operations). The Act only applies to areas within EU law and provides exemptions e.g., for systems that are exclusively used for military and defence as well as for research purposes.

Furthermore, the AI Act outlines rules which follow a risk-based approach, setting clear boundaries by prohibiting certain uses of AI that are deemed unacceptable due to their potential impact on safety and fundamental rights. It also establishes detailed requirements for high-risk AI systems, which require thorough assessments and mandates transparency for systems with limited risks, ensuring users are well-informed about their interactions with AI.

The categories of risks described in the AI Act can be briefly described as per the below:

- **Prohibited AI Practices** include for instance, the use of subliminal techniques that manipulate individuals without their awareness, exploiting vulnerabilities such as age or disability to cause harm, systems of social scoring that may lead to unfair treatment, unauthorised collection of facial images for creating recognition databases as well as the use of AI for predictive policing

based on profiling and systems that use biometric data to group individuals according to specific categories such as race, religion, or sexual orientation.

- **High-Risk AI Systems** are classified based on their intended use and the potential impact on safety and fundamental rights. AI systems are classified as high-risk:
 - if they are used as safety components of products or are themselves products that fall under specific legislation listed in Annex I of the AI Act and if they require to undergo a third-party conformity assessment under these legislations;
 - if they fall among the systems enlisted in Annex III of the AI Act, which include systems used in critical infrastructure, education, employment, essential services, law enforcement, and more.
- The **Systemic risk** category focuses on capable general-purpose AI systems that exceed a certain threshold concerning computational power used to train them.
- **Limited risk** category includes AI systems that are permitted but that require compliance with transparency obligations as well as adherence to copyright protection.
- **Minimal risk** category includes all remaining AI systems that are permitted without any restrictions.

The AI Act requires the design and development of AI systems in a way that achieves an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity, and perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle. The AI Act will be fully applicable twenty-four (24) months after its entry into force (2 August 2026). Bans on prohibited practices will however be applicable six (6) months after the entry into force (2 February 2025); the dispositions on: notifying authorities and notified bodies, general-purpose AI models, governance, confidentiality, and the final dispositions will be fully applicable twelve (12) months after entry into force (2 August 2025); and the dispositions on harmonised products (i.e. High Risk systems under Annex I that require a third party conformity assessment) will be applicable thirty-six (36) months after entry into force of the AI Act (2 August 2027). A more detailed description of the text of the AI Act is set out in the D1.1 v2 (M18) DMP. The section below, however, highlights the specific limitations on the use of AI systems, which can indirectly impact freedoms of speech and explores risk definition and categories in greater depth.

3.1.2.3.1 Risks of prohibited AI practices

This section examines practices involving AI which are prohibited under Article 5 of the AI Act. Some of the prohibited practices under the Act present a negative impact to democracy from the perspective of governments, companies, and organisations. For example, AI systems that manipulate behaviour as outlined under Article 5(1)(a) of the AI Act, or exploit vulnerabilities, can undermine public trust in government institutions. One significant risk caused by AI is the potential for spreading false information. AI-generated deepfakes can deceive voters and erode confidence in the electoral system.

This may result in erosion of trust in government when citizens feel manipulated or unfairly treated and therefore, the citizens' confidence in democratic processes and institutions diminish. If governments employ such manipulative AI techniques, it could influence public opinion and behaviour without the public's awareness. For example, while the use of AI systems has the potential to improve

the efficiency and accuracy of elections, its use may also sway voters' opinions and thereby undermine the fairness and integrity of elections (UN Regional Information Centre for Western Europe; 2024b).

Some of the prohibitions on the deployment of AI systems include those that:

- Use subliminal or manipulative techniques that distort a person's behaviour, leading them to make uninformed decisions, causing harm.
- Exploit vulnerabilities (e.g., based on age, disability, or social status) to distort behaviour and cause harm.
- Evaluate or classify people based on social behaviour, leading to unjust or disproportionate treatment.
- Profile or assess personality traits solely to predict criminal behaviour.
- Expand facial recognition databases through untargeted scraping of internet images or CCTV footage.
- Infer emotions in workplaces or educational institutions, unless for medical or safety purposes.
- Categorise individuals based on biometric data (e.g., race, political opinions).
- Use real-time remote biometric identification in public spaces for law enforcement, except in specific, necessary cases.

The deployment of AI systems that are used to carry out social scoring as outlined under Article 5(1)(c) of the AI Act may present a threat to privacy, human rights provided under the EU Charter and civil liberties. Such practices can lead to mass surveillance and may cultivate an environment of fear and repression, and thereby negatively impact the freedom of assembly and expression under Articles 11 and 12 of the EU Charter, respectively (Article 19, 2018b). This is due to the fact that citizens may fear receiving a negative social score and this might lead individuals to self-censor and therefore limit their freedom of speech (Northeastern Global News, 2024).

The deployment of AI systems that may exploit vulnerabilities of specific groups, e.g., children, disabled individuals, or those in socio-economically disadvantaged positions, to distort behaviour in a way that causes significant harm as outlined under Article 5(1)(c) of the AI Act may undermine the principle of equality in a democracy. This is because AI systems that produce biased results can perpetuate harmful stereotypes, marginalise minority communities, and bring about societal divisions and inequalities (WFD, 2023). As already mentioned in Section 2.1.2.2, AI systems frequently rely on existing datasets that may harbour biases or mirror historical and structural inequalities impacting marginalised groups (O'Neill 2016, Eubanks 2018). Consequently, these systems can perpetuate or even intensify these biases and inequalities in their outputs, resulting in discriminatory decisions that undermine the principle of equal treatment in democratic societies (FRA 2020; 2022).

Similarly, the use of AI systems for making risk assessments of individuals, especially in predicting criminal behaviour based solely on profiling or personality traits as outlined under Article 5(1)(d) of the AI Act, can have profound impacts on democracy. The use of AI systems that are used to predict criminal behaviour that are trained on biased data can result in unfair treatment of certain groups, and thereby undermining justice and equality (TechUK, 2024). Moreover, this predictive policing often relies on historical crime data and may not allow for public input or understanding on how decisions on policing and resources are made. This presents a lack of transparency on the use of predictive

policing tools, including the data sources, methodologies, and impact assessments (Albert Meijer, 2019).

The use of AI systems to create or expand facial recognition databases through untargeted scraping of facial images from the internet or CCTV footage and the use of 'real-time' remote biometric identification (RBI) systems in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement, may lead to mass surveillance as outlined under Articles 5(1)(e) and (h) of the AI Act, and has several profound effects on democracy and freedom of individuals. Such practices may also cultivate an environment of fear from citizens who may feel that they are constantly being watched, and thereby negatively impact the freedom of expression (Article 19, 2018b). Whilst Facial Recognition Technology systems have the capability of preventing severe crimes and detecting suspects, such systems often provide inaccurate or biased results which may ultimately pose a risk to the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens (Internet Policy Review, 2023).

The use of AI systems to infer emotions in workplaces and educational institutions as outlined under Article 5(1)(f) of the AI Act has several risks to the freedoms of individuals. For example, the use of Emotion AI can result in the violation of individuals' right to privacy as provided under Articles 7 and 8 of the EU Charter. Moreover, the constant surveillance of individuals may result in the individuals feeling uncomfortable. This may negatively impact the employees attitudes and perceptions towards their employer and also expose workers to unwanted monitoring and productivity management practices that risk employee privacy (ACM Digital Library; 2023).

3.1.2.3.2 High-Risk AI systems

Pursuant to Art. 6(1) of the AI Act, AI system shall be considered to be high-risk where both of the following conditions are fulfilled:

- the AI system is intended to be used as a safety component of a product, or the AI system is itself a product, covered by the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex I;
- the product whose safety component pursuant to point above is the AI system, or the AI system itself as a product, is required to undergo a third-party conformity assessment, with a view to the placing on the market or the putting into service of that product pursuant to the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex I.

In addition to the above, Article 6(2) provides that AI systems referred to in Annex III of the AI Act shall be considered to be high-risk (unless subject to derogations), i.e.:

- remote biometric identification systems, systems intended to be used for biometric categorization and for emotion recognition (unless they are prohibited);
- managing critical infrastructure (e.g., transport, gas, electricity, digital infrastructure);
- educational and vocational training (e.g., evaluating students' performances);
- employment, workers management and access to self-employment (e.g., assessing employees' performance);
- providing essential private and public services (e.g., credit scoring, access to healthcare, life/health insurance);

- law enforcement (e.g., assessing the risk of recidivism);
- managing migration, asylum, or assessing international protection status;
- administration of justice and democratic processes, influencing voters and the outcome of elections.

The main obligations applicable to providers of High-risk AI systems are summarised below.

Compliance with requirements: comply with the requirements set forth in Section 2 of Chapter III of the AI Act, i.e., Articles 8-15 of the AI Act. In the case of systems that fall under Section 6(1) of the AI Act, suppliers are also responsible for ensuring that the product complies with the harmonising legislation. These requirements include, in particular:

Risk management system: establish, implement, document and maintain appropriate risk assessment and mitigation systems.

Data and data governance: ensure high quality of datasets, address bias and minimise risk of unlawful discrimination (training, validation and testing data).

Technical documentation: prepare detailed technical documentation, providing all necessary information about the system and its purpose to enable authorities to assess its compliance.

Record keeping: ensure that records are kept of the activity to ensure traceability of results.

Transparency and provision of information to deployers: provide clear information and instructions to the deployer to interpret the system output and use it appropriately.

Human oversight : enabling appropriate measures of human supervision by designing and developing systems in such a way that they can be effectively supervised by a physical person (e.g., through appropriate human-machine interface tools).

Accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity: designing systems in such a way as to achieve an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity; (Article 15 of the AI Act).

Quality management system: having a quality management system that ensures compliance with the AI Act. This system shall be documented in a systematic and orderly manner in the form of written policies, procedures and instructions and shall include the aspects listed in Article 17 of the AI Act.

Conformity assessment: before the high-risk AI system is placed on the market, submit it to a conformity assessment procedure on the above obligations, to be carried out by the supplier itself or by a monitoring body.

Registration: before placing a high-risk IA system on the market or putting it into service, register it in an EU-wide database.

High-risk AI systems under Annex III of the EU AI Act can significantly impact democracy and individual freedoms in several ways. For example, the use of AI systems in migration, asylum, and border control management can potentially undermine democracy. This is due to the fact that such systems often involve extensive surveillance and therefore, may lead to an infringement of the right to freedom and privacy of individuals. Moreover, the use of biased AI systems may lead to discriminatory practices against vulnerable groups e.g., migrants and asylum seekers and can therefore result in social inequalities and thereby undermine the rights and freedoms of individuals (European Migration Network, 2022).

While the use of AI for law enforcement and in the administration of justice can enhance the efficiency and accuracy of law enforcement operations, their use may have significant impacts on democracy and freedom. For example, if AI systems are used to make verdicts about the guilt or innocence of accused persons, any biases in the data or algorithms can lead to unfair outcomes. This can undermine the principle of a fair trial and thereby make it difficult for accused persons to understand how decisions are made. This lack of transparency in judicial processes will ultimately make it difficult to effect the right to appeal a decision. Balancing the benefits of AI with the protection of civil liberties is essential to maintaining trust in the justice system and upholding democratic values.

3.1.2.4 Relevant Guidelines on Facial Recognition

Facial recognition technologies (FRTs) are biometric systems that are widely used in the EU context. They provide a very intrusive surveillance power as algorithmic technologies. Debate around FRTs has fuelled the discussion of the AI Act (Giuseppe Mobilo, 2023a). The EDPS defines Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) as “a technology that analyses facial expressions from both static images and videos in order to reveal information on one’s emotional state (EDPS, 2021a).” The EDPS further recognizes that the complexity of facial expressions and the potential use of the technology in any context, and the involvement of new technologies such as AI poses potential risks (EDPS, 2021b).

There are rules on the use of FRTs under the AI Act in that it lays down exceptions for the use of “real time” remote biometric identification in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement. This use is permitted only under strict conditions, such as in cases where it is necessary to find missing persons, prevent imminent threats to life or safety, or identify suspects involved in serious criminal offenses. Moreover, law enforcement must meet stringent safeguards, including judicial authorization, performance of a fundamental rights impact assessment, and registration in the EU’s high-risk AI database.

More precisely, certain remote biometric processing practices are prohibited by Article 5 of the AI Act due to their potential to infringe on fundamental rights and freedoms.

- Article 5(1)(e) prohibits the untargeted scraping of facial images from public sources, such as the internet or CCTV footage, for the creation or expansion of facial recognition databases. This practice involves harvesting vast amounts of biometric data without the knowledge or consent of individuals, raising significant privacy and ethical concerns. By banning this, the AI Act aims to prevent mass surveillance and the unchecked accumulation of sensitive data that could be used for profiling or surveillance without adequate oversight.
- Article 5(1)(g) prohibits the use of facial recognition technologies for biometric categorization that infers sensitive personal characteristics, such as race, political opinions, religious beliefs, or sexual orientation. The danger in allowing AI systems to deduce such traits from biometric data is that it can lead to discriminatory profiling and unjust treatment based on sensitive and deeply personal information. For instance, using facial recognition to infer someone's religious beliefs or sexual orientation without their knowledge could result in unfair treatment, social exclusion, or targeting by authorities or private entities. While some exceptions exist in the context of law enforcement, these are tightly controlled to

prevent abuse and ensure the system is used only for legitimate and legal investigative purposes.

In addition to this, AI systems entailing biometric recognition, when not prohibited as per Article 5 of the AI Act, are likely to fall within the high- risk systems described under Annex III of the AI Act, i.e.:

- Remote biometric identification systems (excluding AI systems intended to be used for biometric verification the sole purpose of which is to confirm that a specific natural person is the person he or she claims to be);
- AI systems that categorise individuals based on biometric data, such as facial features, voice or gait;
- AI systems designed to analyse biometric data to determine an individual's emotional state.

3.1.2.4.1 EDPB Guidelines on Facial Recognition

The EDPB adopted a final version of its Guidelines on facial recognition in the area of law enforcement. Generally, the guidelines serve as a guidance to EU and state legislators, and also law enforcement authorities in the implementation and use of FRTs. The Guidelines emphasise that the Facial recognition tools should only be used in compliance with the Law Enforcement Directive (LED). Furthermore, such tools should only be used if necessary and proportionate as per the Charter (Guidelines 05/2022 on the use of facial recognition technology in the area of law enforcement, 2023a)

The Guidelines also provide that the legal basis must be clear in terms to give citizens an adequate indication on the conditions and circumstances in which authorities may resort to any measures relating to the collection of data and secret surveillance. The Guidelines also recognize that law enforcement authorities have sovereign powers and, FRT faces the risk of interfering with fundamental rights, also beyond the right to protection of personal data and this may have an overall effect on the citizens social and democratic political stability. The application of FRT by enforcement authorities has significant implications on individuals and on groups of people, including minorities. These Guidelines further recognize that the implications have considerable effects on the way we live together and on our social and democratic political stability (Guidelines 05/2022 on the use of facial recognition technology in the area of law enforcement, 2023b). The data of citizens thus has to be processed in a manner that guarantees the effectiveness of the EU data protection rules and principles.

It is also important to note that EU DPAs also have shown their scepticism about facial recognition systems. For example, the Italian data protection authority imposed a data protection fine of EUR 20 million on Clearview AI, a US company offering facial recognition solutions. The Facial Emotion Recognition journal by the EDPS is relevant in identifying some of the risks of using facial recognition and artificial intelligence. It mentions that if the training data is not diverse enough, the technology might be biased against a group of people that is not represented (Facial Emotion Recognition-EDPS, 2021b). It also states that public surveillance cameras may capture expressions during their use and in these situations, transparency issues concerning both the collection and the further processing of personal data may arise.

In the subsequent sections, we will analyse the main elements of the EDPB Guidelines on facial recognition in the area of law enforcement and also the Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition.

3.1.2.4.2 The CoE 108 on Facial Recognition

The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition outline a set of guidelines that governments, facial recognition developers, manufacturers, service providers and entities using FRTs should apply in order to guarantee that such technology does not adversely affect the human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms of citizens, including their right to protection of personal data (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021a).

Legislators and decision makers need to take into consideration the lawfulness of processing when considering the prohibition of processing using FRTs, and need to involve supervisory authorities during the legislative process. The Guidelines stipulate that developers, manufactures and service providers need to ensure the quality of data and algorithms in the use of FRT to avoid adverse effects on individuals. They need to guarantee the reliability of the tools used and respect the rights of data subjects. Entities using FRTs need to ensure that the data security principle is guaranteed. This means that strong security measures should be implemented to protect facial recognition data and image sets against loss and unauthorised access (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021b).

The use of live FRT that is coupled with the risk towards human rights and freedoms should be subject to a democratic debate prior to its use. These rights of data subject may only be restricted when such limitation is provided for by law, it respects the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and constitutes a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society for specific legitimate purposes (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021c).

3.1.2.4.3. Challenges and Opportunities

The existing and proposed legislation governing AI, big data, and frontier technologies presents both challenges and opportunities for fostering democracy. One such opportunity is the “EU Brussels effect,” which enables Europe to set high standards globally. By establishing rigorous rules through current and proposed legislation, the EU can lead the way in promoting democracy and encouraging other nations to adopt similar or even higher standards. Effective EU regulations can perpetuate this effect, shaping international norms in a way that protects democratic values.

However, regulatory compliance, especially for small companies, can be challenging. Although it may seem burdensome, it is essential for protecting consumers and mitigating the risks posed by frontier technologies, including AI. Political pressure also plays a key role in strengthening democracy, as citizens influence government policies to favor public interests, driving the creation of legislation that protects citizens' rights and promotes democratic governance.

The use of facial recognition technologies (FRTs) and AI in general can significantly impact individuals and society. High-risk scenarios, particularly those that may infringe on individual rights and freedoms, need to be carefully defined. Challenges such as algorithmic fairness and accuracy issues in facial recognition systems can lead to discrimination based on factors like skin colour and ethnic origin. Cultural differences in emotional expression may also result in biases in facial emotion recognition systems, potentially preventing certain groups from accessing services due to errors in detecting emotions correctly.

Despite these challenges, FRTs offer opportunities, particularly in enhancing security, public order, and border control. If guidelines on the use of FRTs are followed, these technologies can be deployed effectively, contributing to a secure and orderly society, which in turn fosters democracy by ensuring the safety and rights of citizens.

3.2 Conclusions

This section has provided an analysis of how AI, big data and frontier technologies impact rights from the data protection and general human rights perspective. It has provided a legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies, which includes knowledge technologies, as well as the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising, and in particular, facial recognition and political advertising. Additionally, it has provided an analysis of the risks for data transfers to negatively impact democracy and fundamental rights and highlight the risks or challenges and opportunities in terms of rights and democracy with respect to frontier technologies.

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Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

@kt4democracy.bsky.social

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